

Fostering the communication ecosystem

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The symbiosis between organisms living together in the same environment and their concatenation to evolve towards better states of well-being roughly defines a natural ecosystem, but the concept also carries over into other fields. In communication it involves the public, private and community sectors, institutions, technology providers and relationships with other systems to supply inputs and deliver their achievements in order to achieve freedom of expression.

Although not formally evidenced, interactions between communication actors do occur, and are even mentioned in the Organic Law on Communication. However, the absence of a common agenda is a hindrance to opportunities.

It would be expected that the regulatory body would encourage association, however, the situation of insecurity and Covid-19 have distanced these aspirations. As a result, journalists, academia, content creators and local authorities must work together to propose guarantees for the exercise of journalism, the allocation of state advertising, the programming of public media as a complement to private media, youth entrepreneurship, new academic offerings, quality audiovisual fiction and a host of other desires that will result in employment, but above all in tolerance, peace and democracy.

In the recent local authority elections, few candidates addressed communication issues. Most politicians continue to see radio, TV and social networks as propaganda windows, not understanding that communication is about much more. In the face of this, it is worth trying to promote the communication ecosystem of Ecuador's Zone 7 from the perspective of the protagonists and young filmmakers, with the contribution of universities.